

Demographics and Questionnaire

„Vision Videos and Eye Tracking“

Software Engineering Group, Leibniz Universität Hannover

P-ID

Date:

Questions about the content of the vision videos

Order:

Method A: How long do you need to focus the product with the camera to place an order?

Method B: What happens if you push the button multiple times in a row?

Method C: What is ordered when the fill-level display switches to „EMPTY“?

Delivery:

Method 1: How could the neighbor identify herself to pick up the package?

Method 2: How was the drone delivery coordinated?

Method 3: How does the access to the recipient's trunk work?

Do you have ideas for different ordering or delivery options?

Did the texts help to understand the visions?

Totally disagree

Totally agree

Was the positioning of the texts appropriate in your opinion?

Totally disagree

Totally agree

Please give reasons for your opinion:

Please rate the following statements and questions according to the respective scale

- *How much mental effort did you invest while watching the vision videos?*

Very, very low
mental effort
(Riding a bike)

Very, very high
mental effort
(writing
an exam)

- *I liked the videos.*

Totally disagree

Totally agree

- *The videos provide important information to me.*

Totally disagree

Totally agree

- *The video quality was sufficient to understand the content.*

Totally disagree

Totally agree

- *The videos encourage me to think about the shown subject.*

Totally disagree

Totally agree

- *The texts provide important information to me.*

Totally disagree

Totally agree

- *I liked the form/ modality (color, size, font) of the texts.*

Totally disagree

Totally agree

Please give reasons for your opinion:

Do you have suggestions to improve the form/ modality of the texts?

- no
- yes

If yes, which improvement suggestions do you have?

Demographical Data

My age is _____.

Information about gender:

- male
- female
- other
- prefer not to say

